

RLUK Research Libraries UK

Developing inclusive collections:
understanding current practices and
needs of RLUK research libraries

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CONTENTS

Acknowledgements.....	2
Executive Summary.....	3
Introduction.....	4
Methodology.....	4
Survey Findings.....	5
Participants.....	5
Developing strategic approaches to decolonisation.....	7
Decolonisation drivers in RLUK institutions.....	9
Decolonisation in practice.....	11
Professional Roles, Skills and Training.....	16
Discussion.....	24
Conclusion.....	26
References.....	27
Appendix.....	28

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the results of a recent survey launched by Research Library UK (RLUK) aiming to document the current practices and needs of member institutions when developing initiatives that aim to make collections more diverse and inclusive. The focus was placed on decolonisation efforts and the needs of professionals that lead or support them in terms of training and skills development. The motivation behind the survey was to understand the challenges that research libraries currently face with regards to decolonisation practice with the aim of providing more targeted support for the RLUK community.

The survey was designed by the RLUK Decolonisation Group and received 61 responses from 33 different RLUK institutions. Below are the headline findings of the report:

- **Variety of activity and stages of progress:** Most RLUK member libraries were found to actively engage in decolonisation activities or other initiatives that aim to contribute towards tackling biases in collections as well as diversifying them and contributing towards the development of equitable practices. Yet, they all seem to be at different levels of progress with a variety of challenges faced in individual institutions depending on the employed approach.
- **Decolonisation in strategy:** Several institutions had some type of working definition, statement, or strategy describing the library's intentions with regards to decolonisation or, more generally, to making collections more inclusive and representative of its communities. On the other hand, many research libraries have not yet embedded decolonisation or relevant initiatives in their strategic objectives; this was found to result in challenges for staff, from justifying the time allocated to engage in relevant initiatives and training to advocating about the necessity of this work to other library staff and stakeholders.
- **Organising decolonisation in research libraries:** Grassroot decolonisation or equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) groups were found to constitute the main forces in leading discussions and developing relevant initiatives in many RLUK member institutions. Also, decolonisation initiatives have been found to be overwhelmingly funded from within the library or home institution. A common problem related to how decolonisation was organised in member institutions was that relevant activities could be scattered. Hence, it was challenging to learn what others were doing and, for this reason, there was a call for a more strategic approach to decolonisation that coordinates efforts.
- **Staff confidence:** This study found that a combination of direct involvement in decolonisation activities and participation in relevant groups which enabled the sharing of ideas with colleagues, together with events attendance and consultation of training and other relevant resources produced by the broader cultural heritage sector had a positive impact on confidence levels. On the other hand, allocating decolonisation responsibilities to just one or very few professionals without providing further support was found to negatively affect staff confidence, even if colleagues had an expert skillset.
- **Support and training:** Given the lack of formal guidelines for libraries on how to implement decolonisation, library professionals will find different types of support and training helpful, from information on how to get started with reviewing existing collection policies and practices to engaging with stakeholders and contributing to the decolonisation of the curriculum in their home institution. Some of this type of support and training may be better provided by individual institutions (e.g. stakeholder engagement), while other initiatives, such as developing and sharing glossaries or cases of best practice, will need to be developed in collaboration with the community. Prioritising decolonisation in library strategic agendas as well as providing spaces where difficult conversations with colleagues and, potentially, stakeholders can take place were considered valuable for achieving progress in the area and increasing staff confidence.
- **The role of the sector:** Sector-wide discussions and conversations with others supporting Higher Education institutions, the sharing of best practice, and the identification of collaborative opportunities were considered essential for advancing decolonisation work and collectively advocating for inclusive collections and equitable practices.

INTRODUCTION

Over recent years, Higher Education and collection-holding institutions in the UK and beyond have been striving to become more representative of the communities they serve. As a result, a variety of programmes and activities have emerged that aim to transform scholarship and learning through increasing diversity in collections and employing inclusive approaches to pedagogy.

Decolonisation as a practice has increasingly gained a prominent place in the strategic agenda of academic and research libraries as a way to re-contextualise collections, combat biases and uncover hidden voices. Many Research Libraries UK (RLUK) institutions have engaged in decolonisation activities as part of their goals to develop inclusive collections and equitable practices and contribute towards broader decolonisation efforts in their home institutions.

There is a growing body of literature examining issues related to decolonisation and the role of research and academic libraries as well as the approaches currently employed by institutions in the UK (e.g. see [Clarke, 2020](#); [Crilly, 2019](#); [Crilly and Everitt, 2021](#); [Wilson, 2021](#)). These form part of the broader decolonial dialogue in the Higher Education and cultural heritage sectors nationally and internationally which also includes debates around what decolonisation is and whether or how it can be achieved (e.g. [Charles, 2019](#); [Adebisi 2019](#); [Adebisi, 2020](#); [Bhambra, Gebrial, and Nişancioğlu, 2020](#); [Rangan, 2021](#); [Adefila et al., 2022](#); [Winter, Webb and Turner, 2022](#)). It is worth acknowledging the large number of conferences and events as well as community discussions that have focused on the topic recently, some of which have led to the development of collaborative resources and tools for the Higher Education and cultural heritage sectors (e.g. [Museum Association's 'Decolonising Museums' guidance](#), [Decolonisation Best Practice and Case Studies in HE Libraries](#)).

In this context, many RLUK libraries have issued statements, developed decolonisation toolkits and guidance as well as published examples of their practice demonstrating how they actively engage in the decolonisation of collections and the curriculum in their home institutions. Several have also established institutional groups and forums where related issues can be discussed with stakeholders.

This report is based on a survey, which was launched by RLUK in December 2022, looking at current practices and needs of RLUK libraries when making collections more inclusive, with a focus on decolonisation practices and understanding the training needs and skills requirements that staff in member institutions may have. Ultimately, documenting any gaps and challenges that research libraries face with regards to decolonisation practice can lead to more targeted support for the RLUK community.

METHODOLOGY

The survey, which was launched in December 2022 and closed in February 2023, was circulated across the RLUK membership. It was designed by the RLUK Decolonisation Group, which consists of members of the RLUK Special Collections and Heritage Network (SCHN) and the RLUK Collections Strategy Network (CSN) and is chaired by the RLUK Executive.

The group began meeting in January 2022 to discuss issues of common interest around the decolonisation of collections in research libraries. Through conducting preliminary work ([Kamposiori, 2022](#)), the group discovered that capacity and confidence building through training and skills development was a key need related to decolonisation practice that collection-holding institutions have. Thus, two pieces of work were developed. The first was the RLUK Seminar Series '[Inclusive Collections, Inclusive Libraries \(ICIL\)](#)' which aims to foster conversation around decolonisation and inclusive practice in collecting, describing, presenting, and engaging with content in research library collections.

The second piece of work was a survey, the results of which are presented here, and which aimed to capture the strategic priorities of RLUK research libraries with regards to making collections more inclusive and diverse, including their practices around decolonisation. Moreover, the survey included questions that aimed to explore the practices of individuals within these organisations as well as their training and skills requirements. Highlighting examples of good practice and facilitating knowledge exchange and community building in the area through sharing these examples also constituted part of the goals of this study.

It should be noted that RLUK members could provide more than one response per institution so that the different needs of professionals leading or supporting decolonisation activities in member institutions could be documented and understood. The questionnaire included a combination of different types of questions, such as multiple choice and open-ended questions to capture the different circumstances of member institutions and the professionals completing the survey. The findings presented in this report have been anonymised.

Regarding the definition of decolonisation that was employed for the purposes of this study, it is a broad one. It focuses on the work that research libraries are currently doing to diversify and enrich their collections in order to make diverse voices heard and uncover ‘hidden’ histories. It also relates to the shift in current practice through challenging existing biases in our collections and the way we work. However, the RLUK Decolonisation Group acknowledges that there is a variety of definitions used by libraries and other organisations to refer to their work around decolonisation and increasing diversity of collections, some of which have been developed in collaboration with stakeholders.

SURVEY FINDINGS

Participants

The survey received 61 responses from 33 different RLUK institutions. From these research libraries, 18 institutions submitted 1 response each, while 10 libraries submitted 2 responses each. The remaining 5 institutions submitted more than 2 responses each, with 1 library submitting 9 responses. Joint responses were submitted by professionals in two institutions; since they included named comments, these were counted as separate responses. Finally, 1 institution submitted 2 responses by the same professional; given that the second response was similar to the first but more detailed, a decision was made to exclude the first response from the analysis of the collected data.

Table 1 lists the participating institutions, in which at least half of those participating in the study gave their consent for their institution to be cited.

Regarding the profile of the professionals completing the survey, these came from across the different areas of the library. Examples of the variety of roles involved in decolonisation initiatives include:

- Head of Collections; Head of Collection Development; Head of Library Resources and Collections; Collections Manager; Head of Access and Acquisitions; Curator; Head of Special Collections and Archives; Head of Collection Strategy; Lead Archivist
- Head of Liaison and Academic Services; Subject Librarian; Library Assistant; Academic Support Librarian; Liaison Librarian; Arts & Humanities Librarian; Genetics Librarian
- Head of Scholarly Communications Management; Head of Research and Learning Information Services; Bibliographic Services Manager
- Head of User Experience; Library Teaching; Project Support Officer
- Deputy/ Associate Director; University/ School Librarian

Thus, based on our findings it became apparent that some had collections as their primary area of responsibility, while others were working closely with academics and students.

Table 1 Participating Institutions

Participating Institution	No. of responses
1. RLUK Member Library	1
2. University of Liverpool Library	2
3. Newcastle University Library	2
4. University of Leicester Library	2
5. School of Oriental and African Studies (SOAS) Library	2
6. RLUK Member Library	1
7. RLUK Member Library	1
8. Cambridge University and College Libraries	9
9. King's College London Library	1
10. Durham University Library and Collections	1
11. Imperial College London Library	2
12. University College London Library	1
13. University of St Andrews Libraries & Museums	1
14. University of Southampton Library	1
15. University of Exeter Library	1
16. Queen's University Belfast Library	1
17. University of Nottingham Libraries	2
18. University of Edinburgh Library	1
19. National Library of Scotland	1
20. Queen Mary University of London Library	3
21. University of Warwick Library	4
22. RLUK Member Library	1
23. Cardiff University Library	1
24. University of Sheffield Library	3
25. Library of Trinity College Dublin	1
26. Glasgow University Library	2
27. University of Aberdeen Library	2
28. University of York Library	1
29. University of Bristol Library	4
30. University of Sussex Library	2
31. University of Leeds Library	2
32. University of East Anglia Library	1
33. Senate House Library	1
Total of responses	61

Participants were at different career levels. However, the majority held medium to high seniority roles, while some participants were members of the leadership teams of some libraries.

The fact that participants from a variety of roles were currently leading, supporting, or were about to be involved in decolonisation activities demonstrates that related initiatives are not driven only by professionals with specific roles or backgrounds. Given the variety of backgrounds and expertise, it may also be fair to assume that these professionals may have different needs in terms of training and skills development around decolonisation.

Developing strategic approaches to decolonisation

Thinking about whether RLUK member libraries are currently involved or planning to get involved in decolonisation initiatives [Fig. 1], the majority of participants answered that their libraries do engage in relevant activities. Few participants said that they did not know or were not sure, while the comments by two participants under 'Other' aimed to highlight that related activities were being led by another team in the library or that some activities were taking place but were not branded as 'decolonisation' activities.

Is your Library currently involved in decolonisation activities?

Figure 1 RLUK libraries' involvement in decolonisation activities

Participants, through the provision of qualitative comments, elaborated on the types of activities their organisations are currently engaged in. Examples of initiatives undertaken can be related to collections, such as collections analysis and revision of collection policies as well as work on revising language in metadata and cataloguing. Various projects were focusing on making collections more transparent and inclusive or investigating the provenance of collections. Some of these were conducted in collaboration with academics and other communities as well as other centres with an interest on the topic and departments responsible for collections (e.g. museums and galleries) within the home institution.

Several referred to their library's involvement in decolonising the curriculum in their home institutions. Relevant activities involved providing online reading list data to departments currently reviewing their curricula and, generally, advising academics through providing useful resources. Some institutions have already developed relevant tools for the decolonisation of collections or the decolonisation of the curriculum, or written guides to decolonising reading lists. Others are mapping reading lists to assess their diversity and looking to a wider range of suppliers for content to support academics.

Additionally, many professionals in this study mentioned the establishment of internal equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI), decolonisation, and other groups to support initiatives led by or developed for colleagues and users from minority backgrounds, while representation at external groups focusing on these issues was also frequent. Organising and attending events, such as seminars and workshops, as well as delivering sessions to engage with different communities on the topic were activities led by many institutions. Some were also communicating about relevant work in the library through online and digital media (library website, blogs). Paid student curatorships and internships with a focus on making collections more inclusive and diverse were taking place in few institutions.

Finally, there were references to the strategic work of some RLUK research libraries in the area which helped contribute towards their home institution's EDI goals, such as formulating guidance and policy relating to EDI within the University's collections, developing strategies to tackle institutional legacies, or having dedicated budget for relevant initiatives.

However, when asked about whether their library or institution had a working definition, strategy or statement around decolonisation [Fig. 3], answers were divided. More than a third of institutions said that they do not have a working definition, strategy or statement around decolonisation, while about another one third said that they do. The remaining, approximately, one third said that they were not sure, did not know or chose 'Other'. From those choosing 'other', some said that they have provided or are planning to provide some context around decolonisation in existing strategies around collections.

Do you have a working definition, strategy or statement around decolonisation in your library and/ or institution?

Figure 2 Do you have a working definition, strategy or statement around decolonisation in your library and/ or institution?

Some of the participants provided further information about their working definitions, statements, and strategies around decolonisation. These comments frequently included statements and definitions that mentioned the fact that many research libraries' collections include content relating to minority and marginalised groups which is often 'hidden'. The need for re-contextualising collections was highlighted, alongside the need to be explicit and transparent around issues of origin related to institutional collections; not doing so could have a negative impact on library communities, research, and teaching.

Other survey respondents referred to the stated EDI values and objectives of the home institution or the library, or provided links to the terms of references of decolonisation groups established in the library which included expressions of commitment in the area. Links to institutional websites with information about current activity to diversify collections or to decolonise the curriculum were also included. Moreover, some of the libraries which had definitions around decolonisation were emphasising the collaborative work they were doing with stakeholders, such as students, to tackle any biases and structural inequalities in the collections and other areas of the library.

It is worth noting that some libraries were not using the word ‘decolonising’ to refer to relevant activities in their statements, definitions, and programmes of activity, but preferred to use words such as ‘diversifying’ and ‘liberating’ collections and practices. Few were also recognising in their statements that existing biases in collections were directly related to the lack of a diverse workforce.

Decolonisation drivers in RLUK institutions

Regarding the most common reasons [see Fig. 3] for developing and engaging in decolonisation activities, these were: to support underrepresented communities and voices (88.52%), to support teaching and the curriculum (83.61%), and to engage with the student community (73.77%). However, as it becomes apparent from the below graph, many research libraries had a wider range of goals which were supported by decolonisation initiatives. These included: uncovering ‘hidden histories’ in collections (65.57%), meeting the home institution’s (65.57%) or the library’s EDI strategy (59.02%), engaging with new audiences (55.74%), as well as influencing academic and research practice (50.82%). Some said that their decolonisation activities support work to address awarding (or attainment) gaps between student groups (37.70%), while few participants are involved in related work to meet funder requirements (4.92%), Public Sector Equality Duty (PSED) reporting obligations (1.64%), or for other reasons (4.92%).

Figure 3 Reasons for decolonising collections in RLUK libraries

Clarifications provided by participants on the drivers for decolonisation further confirmed the intentions of member institutions to ensure that institutional collections (special collections, archives, and modern collections) reflect the plurality of voices and experiences in collections, but also current library and university communities. By considering what best practice is and how it can be applied in all areas of collection management, RLUK research libraries aim to be proactive in responding to the shift in research and teaching and providing access to diverse sources to meet the needs of their academics and students. Some libraries aimed to contribute to the home institution’s objectives around race equality and inclusivity and, thus, did not regard decolonisation as strictly library activity.

Understanding the origins of collections and the impact of their colonial legacy on the present and future of the institution was a driver for several RLUK members, while in some organisations staff were driven by a sense of social justice and aspirations to achieve wider recognition of their work. Making connections with a variety of internal and external stakeholders and reaching new audiences with a range of protected characteristics were both drivers and goals for many research libraries engaging in decolonisation activities.

It is worth mentioning some participants' comments showcasing the different routes through which relevant work was developed and progressed. For example, there were cases where personal interest was driving activity in this area. In other cases, grassroots and other stakeholder groups were taking things forward, or formal governance routes were followed. Few comments also revealed the challenges faced in some institutions in developing and maintaining an approach to decolonisation. These ranged from difficulties in deciding the right language to use to issues related to the limited support by the senior executive team within the library; this can, unfortunately, have a negative impact on the work and confidence of staff responsible for relevant activities, especially if there is only one person or few professionals who support these.

Answers to the question of who leads decolonisation activities within RLUK libraries or their home institutions (Fig. 4) offered further insights into those groups or individuals with most responsibility for developing and managing relevant initiatives. More specifically, in just above half of members participating (55.74%), the Decolonisation/ EDI groups in the libraries were the ones driving change in collections and practices. In several institutions, decolonisation efforts were driven by certain individuals in academic departments (49.18%) or the library (42.62%).

At this point, it should be noted that, based on the findings of a recent RLUK report (*Kamposiori, 2022*), there is often a higher emotional toll involved, and it is harder to achieve change when there are only certain individuals responsible for EDI and related activities, compared to when a larger group or everyone in the library is involved. So, this is something that should be taken into account when prioritising decolonisation in an institution, as it can have an impact on the professionals' work as well as their confidence.

Figure 4 Leading decolonisation in RLUK libraries

Besides these, the Decolonisation/ EDI Team or Department in a library's home institution (e.g. university) was mentioned to be the leader of relevant initiatives by 39.34% of participants, while the University Leadership had responsibility for decolonisation in some institutions as per 34.43% of participants. In other organisations, the archive (22.95%) was the leader of relevant initiatives and discussions, whereas few RLUK members (16.39%) said that academic departments were driving things forward in the area. A small percentage of participants (9.84%) said that they were not sure or did not know. Some respondents chose 'Other' (22.95%) to explain that a collaborative or 'bottom-up' approach was followed in their institutions or provide further comments about certain individuals in the University Leadership leading decolonisation (e.g. Pro Vice Chancellor with EDI responsibilities), or specific departments in the library or home institution (e.g. Museums and Special Collections, EDI Office, Centre for Higher Education Practice) which were responsible for relevant initiatives.

It was also very interesting to discover that in some institutions, the students or the student union were credited as the leaders in decolonisation. According to some participants' comments, student activism has been the driving force in this area through hosting events and leading discussions, and challenging academic schools to decolonise practices. Finally, one participant reported difficulty in identifying who was leading decolonisation in their institution given the low visibility of related work, while in another library no one had responsibility for decolonising collections and practices.

How are decolonisation activities funded in your institution?

Figure 5 Funding decolonisation in RLUK libraries

Regarding how decolonisation activities were funded in the participating institutions (Fig. 5), these were found to be overwhelmingly funded by within the library (59.02%) or through the home institution (42.62%). Few organisations reported receiving funding externally, through a funding organisation (4.92%) or other resources (1.64%). There was a significant number of participants who said that they were not sure or did not know, a finding that signifies that some of the structures supporting decolonisation may not be visible to many professionals working in RLUK member institutions. This is particularly surprising given that the majority of those responding to the survey were involved in or supporting relevant initiatives.

Decolonisation in Practice

According to our findings (Fig. 6), teaching collections and reading lists (68.85%) will undergo decolonisation in the majority of participating institutions. Special collections (54.10%) and archives (52.46%) are also candidates for decolonisation based on the answers of more than half of respondents. In almost half of RLUK members completing the survey, decolonising modern collections (49.18%) is part of their strategic plans in the area, while some institutions aim to tackle existing biases in digital collections (31.15%) and museum collections (26.23%). There were few respondents who were not sure or did not know (16.39%) which collections will be subject to decolonisation. Some of the participants choosing 'Other' (11.48%) further explained the nature of relevant work and the way it is organised in their institutions which, in some cases, meant that decolonisation principles will be applied to some extent to different types of collections based on priorities or on a project basis. There was one institution which will also decolonise their leisure reading and fiction collections, while few commented that relevant work has not started yet in their organisations.

Which part(s) of institutional collections are undergoing or will undergo decolonisation?

Figure 6 Types of collections that will undergo decolonisation

Further comments on the types of collections that are prioritised for decolonisation in RLUK member institutions revealed aspects of the decision-making process behind choosing collections to undergo this process. For example, one participant reported that relevant actions will be taken based on the results of a collections evaluation which identified the strengths, but also the gaps in different institutional collections. Others provided more information on the approach they will employ, such as focusing on acquiring more content to diversify their collections, looking at how they can decolonise practices (e.g. looking at language in metadata or reviewing classification systems), or working with other stakeholders to decolonise specific content, such as reading lists. The fact that teaching materials and reading lists are on the top of the priority list for decolonisation as well as the urgency with which this task needs to be accomplished became evident through the answers of several participants.

In few research libraries, decolonisation is not regarded as a separate activity, but related plans are embedded in existing collection review or management strategies. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that many institutions have launched calls to their communities to make recommendations for books and other resources that will contribute towards their goals to build inclusive and diverse collections and balance any current gaps. Others highlighted that a broader approach will be taken in their institutions that will not just focus on decolonisation, but will aim to address issues around eugenics and issues related to underrepresented communities (e.g. LGBTQ+); in some cases, this approach will enable them to access special funds set up for this purpose. Few noted that planning for decolonising collections has not begun yet.

Regarding the methods that RLUK member libraries employ towards tackling biases and injustices in collections, the majority of participating institutions have as a priority to increase diversity in their collections (73.77%). Many research libraries are also reviewing their collection development policies (65.57%), engaging the student community in the process (65.57%), and aiming to enrich metadata and review the language used in headings and descriptions (63.93%). More than half of respondents said that, as part of their strategic goals in the area, they collaborate with academics and researchers in related projects (55.74%), engage with underrepresented communities (e.g. through consultation) (54.10%), display collections in new ways to showcase 'hidden' or 'difficult' histories (54.10%), and engage with EDI groups from the library or home institution (54.10%). Just less than half mentioned revising cataloguing procedures (47.54%) while working towards decolonisation.

Some institutions attempt to embed learning from sector collaboration and engagement (37.70%), while fewer have currently as a priority to improve wayfinding to physical or digital diverse collections (26.23%), or use a specific framework or toolkit (22.95%). A small percentage said that they did not know or were not sure about the organisational approach to decolonisation (6.56%). Some of the comments submitted under 'Other' (8.20%) revealed that relevant activities can be conducted across different departments in some institutions, but the types of activities or the processes followed may not be apparent to others. Finally, few participants commented that some of the listed activities were part of their plans, but they have not been formally implemented yet.

How does your library go about decolonising institutional collections?

Figure 7 Steps undertaken by RLUK libraries to decolonise collections

More information on the steps and methodologies taken towards decolonisation by RLUK member institutions was provided through further qualitative comments by survey participants, which also included examples of interesting projects and work that has been already achieved (e.g. development of toolkits) (see Appendix). The interests and perspectives of staff working in some research libraries also became evident. For example, a participant mentioned that they are interested in the way knowledge is produced and how that impacts on collection development and discovery. Another noted that their team focuses on working on a solution to recognise contentious material content which is reported by users, but without removing it.

Based on some respondents, the recent Covid-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on achieving progress in the area, but it was very positive to read that efforts are picking up again. Yet, there are still barriers to overcome to fully achieve the goals set in some institutions due to issues such as lack of cohesion across the library and the home institution which makes continuity harder to achieve. Allocating relevant responsibilities to one or few individuals instead of a larger group of professionals has also been referenced as one of the problems going forward, which makes it difficult to secure the support needed and negatively affects the confidence of staff.

However, before moving to discuss the benefits and challenges around decolonisation, it is worth discussing in more detail the survey findings around RLUK member libraries' contribution to decolonising the curriculum (Fig. 8). Thus, in approximately half of participating institutions, the library either currently plays an active role in decolonising the curriculum (36.07%) or will do so in the immediate future (21.31%). In a smaller percentage of research libraries (9.84%), there are no plans at the moment to actively contribute towards decolonising the curriculum, while several participants did not know or were not sure (19.67%) about their institution's plans in the area. Many of the comments submitted under 'Other' (13.11%) revealed that more RLUK institutions are involved in supporting the decolonisation of the curriculum but also uncovered the circumstances under which relevant work is conducted; for example, in one institution, relevant advice is provided to academics on an ad hoc basis while, in another, there are only one or two staff members who drive this work forward.

Does the library play an active role in decolonising the curriculum at your home institution?

Figure 8 Does the library play an active role in decolonising the curriculum at your institution?

Through further qualitative comments on the work conducted to decolonise the curriculum, we learnt that research libraries play a key role in the process through providing reading list data and advising academics on the development of inclusive reading lists. Several libraries mentioned providing relevant training to academics but also to students with a focus on how to identify the origin of research outputs. Others highlighted the collaborative nature of this work which requires strong partnerships with internal communities as well as external stakeholders, such as underrepresented communities and others in the Higher Education sector. For example, one institution mentioned opening the dialogue for marginalised voices through creating 'radical' reading lists which exclude Western canons of literature and engaging students as co-creators in activities that aim to challenge existing biases and foster inclusivity. Another participant commented on publication outputs they have produced on the topic in collaboration with others in the sector.

Based on our findings, it also became evident that libraries can play a central role in making connections between departments and teams who may work on similar areas but are unaware about each other's projects. Thus, as it was reported, members of the liaison teams as well as members of the EDI or decolonisation groups in the library were often those who were leading work in this area. However, beside liaising with communities, some participants referred to the work that is conducted behind the scenes to support this agenda. For example, one participant highlighted the fact that acquisition of material that supports EDI principles and the 'decolonising the curriculum' agenda is prioritised, when possible, along with other activities (e.g. cataloguing, signposting) that make this material more visible. Some referred to the user driven approach they employ to collection development and the processes of responding to users

making recommendations for more diverse material or the importance of activities such as reviewing language and subject headings in classification to improve the discovery of useful material for teaching. Few noted that they were just starting to have discussions about the library's role in this area.

Generally, developing and supporting decolonisation initiatives was reported to entail several benefits for the library, home institution, and their communities. Thus, some of the main advantages of prioritising decolonisation and engaging in relevant activities are related to the development of a better understanding of institutional collections and where they originate. Additionally, through diversifying and widening the scope of collections, libraries can better tell the stories of previously underrepresented groups and reflect modern society.

Part of the goals of many institutions is to have richer and more diverse collections which acknowledge history but strive for better practice. In that way, some participants highlighted the responsibility of institutions to better represent modern society and contribute towards social justice by addressing historic inequalities and the power imbalance in collections. Through embarking on decolonisation activities, there are also increased opportunities for engagement with different communities, including academics and students, and the possibility of having a positive impact on research and teaching. Moreover, cultivating a sense of belonging and ownership while engaging with communities through collections can increase their value and impact.

Taking the opportunity to develop and embed best practice around decolonisation can significantly benefit library operations as well, such as through demonstrating the value and importance of back-office activities (e.g. cataloguing, digitisation) to support this agenda. Showcasing the value of relevant activity for achieving the broader EDI goals of the library and the home institution can be particularly useful when raising awareness around decolonisation amongst library staff. The evaluation of collection strengths and gaps in terms of representation can also be useful for identifying areas for further investment, while enhanced catalogue descriptions can improve discoverability of certain content. Finally, some participants were optimistic that overall activity in the area can contribute towards building a more diverse student body and staff.

Thinking about the challenges, lack of staff capacity and limited resources was the most common issue reported by participants throughout the survey. Lack of confidence and expertise was often another barrier that had to be overcome to move things forward. It should be highlighted that the staff enthusiasm and willingness to engage in decolonisation activities was often there; yet, the scale and complexity of the work in combination with the lack of training and the uncertainty of where to start can make it much more difficult to achieve progress.

Additionally, lack of common understanding around decolonisation, including the complexities and sensitivities related to the topic (e.g. around language), as well as concerns about the current political climate and the perception of the role of universities in the 'culture wars' can be deterring factors. Securing buy-in from stakeholders and succeeding to engage ethnic and minority communities (including students) in the process was also essential in moving things forward and, as a result, could affect progress if not achieved.

Some mentioned that the financial implications of developing diverse collections (e.g. buying new content, conducting reclassification etc.) are substantial; a participant mentioned that, in their institution, they have to spread their budget over several years to achieve change in collections which can make it harder to progress in areas such as decolonisation. It is worth noting that, according to participants, financial rules about overseas suppliers can make it harder to buy material to support the decolonisation and EDI agendas. Regarding collections, some thought that building decolonisation into business-as-usual (along with aspects of EDI more generally) was particularly challenging, while certain activities aimed at enhancing collections, such as achieving accuracy and metadata uniformity, were proving to be difficult tasks.

Finally, issues around the management acceptance of the importance of this work can lead to a lack of a clear decolonising strategy which, in turn, can slow progress and affect staff confidence and their work. It was also frequently reported that staff were leading or supporting decolonisation activities on top of other duties and without these being formally part of their formal objectives; an implication in such cases is that it can be harder for staff to justify time for necessary training. Problematic communication across different departments or teams engaged in relevant work, the lack of diversity in the workforce, as well as the resistance and limited interest by some disciplines or individuals to contribute to the decolonisation agenda were some additional obstacles faced within some research libraries.

Professional Roles, Skills and Training

As part of this study, we also aimed to understand the practices and needs, in terms of training and skills development, of the professionals leading or supporting decolonisation activities. Thus, when asked about whether decolonisation was part of their job role or their objectives (Fig. 9), almost half of participants said that decolonisation activities are indeed part of their job, but not formally (47.54%). If you, then, add the percentage of those who said that decolonisation is part of their role or objectives (24.59%), it becomes obvious that most of the participants in this study were actively contributing to the relevant agenda in their institution either formally or not. A small number of respondents said that decolonisation responsibilities were not part of their role (8.20%), while an equal number (8.20%) said a portion of their responsibilities were related to decolonisation. Some chose 'Other' as an opportunity to clarify the types of activities they are involved in (e.g. co-ordinating EDI activities, collection development to support research and teaching) or further comment on the circumstances under which relevant work is conducted in their institution (e.g. built into formal duties where possible, built in institutional strategy but not in objectives yet). Few said that colleagues in their libraries are aware of related discussions and initiatives across the sector, but relevant activity has not begun yet.

Is decolonisation part of your job role and/or your objectives?

Figure 9 Is decolonisation part of your job role and/or your objectives?

Concerning the level of confidence with regards to their understanding about what decolonisation means for their job (Fig. 10), more than half of participants said that they have moderate confidence (63.93%), about a third said that they have high confidence (31.15%), and a small number of participants answered that they have low confidence (8.20%). Through further analysis of the answers submitted by those who said that they have high confidence regarding what decolonisation means for their job, it became evident that almost all participants in this group were involved in decolonisation activities in their institutions and they were active members of internal and external EDI or decolonisation groups.

It is worth noting that in more than half of the institutions where participants said they are confident in this topic, the EDI or decolonisation group in the library was reported to drive decolonisation. Almost all these participants held middle to senior management roles within their institution.

Figure 10 Participants' level of confidence with regards to their understanding of what decolonisation means for their job

Thinking about the provision of decolonisation training for staff in RLUK member institutions participating in this study (Fig. 11), our results showed that only a small percentage of research libraries provide relevant training for all staff (9.84%).

Has your institution provided training for you and other staff about decolonisation?

Figure 11 Has your institution provided training for you and other staff about decolonisation?

About a third of respondents said that their organisation provides training only for some staff members (29.51%), while a significant number of libraries do not provide any training yet; few of those are planning to offer training in the immediate future. There were also some participants who did not know or were not sure (13.11%), while some chose 'Other' (16.39%). Respondents in this latter group either provided examples of other types of training available within their institution (e.g. events on the topic by the Student Union; training on inclusion and racial inclusion from a wider institutional/ HE perspective; training for academics) or explained that, even though formal training is not provided, staff take advantage of other opportunities to develop their knowledge and expertise on the topic (e.g. dialogue within grassroots groups; attending awareness raising and best practice sharing sessions; using 'how to' guides and case studies that have been shared; benefitting from external opportunities, e.g. events).

Concerning the answers by those participants saying they have high confidence in the area, only half said that their institution is providing training and this is offered only to some members of staff. Some in this group said that their institutions are planning to offer training in the near future. Thus, through our findings we were not able to establish a clear link between high confidence and the provision of training alone. On the other hand, direct involvement in decolonisation activities, alongside participation in relevant groups where colleagues' support can be secured, events attendance and the consultation of training and other relevant resources by libraries and others in the broader cultural heritage sector (e.g. museums) were found to have a positive impact on confidence levels.

Examples of the types of training around decolonisation offered by those RLUK institutions whose representatives said that they do provide relevant training can be found in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Types of training provided around decolonisation by some participating RLUK institutions

Series of seminars available for all staff on decolonisation and how it affects the curriculum/ decolonisation of reading lists/ anti-racist pedagogy
White Ally training; Unconscious Bias training; Awareness for race equality charter; Racial Inclusivity Awareness
Self-directed online courses; modules
Reading groups
One-off events locally and external (seminar presentations, workshops etc.), as well as library and academic conferences (internal and external)
Consulting internal and external resources (e.g. blog posts; libguides and toolkits, such as reading list decolonisation 'toolkit'; platform with relevant case studies and other material etc.) and the expertise of leaders in the area (e.g. Museums Association Decolonisation Group)
Sharing case studies and examples of best practice
Training offered as part of collaborative initiative between different organisations
Training by grassroots group of library staff and other groups, e.g. communities of practices, HR
Race equity and other EDI training

Training is often delivered by different groups within the library or home institution (e.g. academic departments, EDI/ decolonisation group, student EDI team, Anti-racist Teaching group; Organisational Development and Professional Learning Team) and is often targeted to academics, professional services staff in managerial positions, or students. In most cases, these focus on issues of inclusivity and diversity, and aim to raise awareness about existing biases, rather than focus exclusively on decolonisation. Yet, some have explored different aspects of this topic, such as decolonising the curriculum and considering the socio-cultural and geo-political contexts related to coloniality, or looking at the implications of decolonisation in other areas of the library's work (open access, reader services, classification).

It should be noted that some have deliberately omitted the word ‘decolonisation’ from the title of the training they provide or the resources they create as it is deemed a conflicting term in their organisation. Some of the participants mentioned that they were the ones responsible for delivering the training or were part of a group responsible to deliver this. Training for students has been designed to give them the tools to consider inherent biases in academic databases and enable them to identify strategies for discovering the work of underrepresented voices.

Regarding participants’ use of community-built or externally created resources as part of developing their knowledge around decolonisation, the vast majority said that they do use such resources as part of training development (75.41%), while few said that they do not use them currently, but they plan to (9.84%). A small number of participants said they do not use such resources (6.56%), or did not know or were not sure (4.92%). Participants choosing ‘Other’ (3.28%) provided examples of resources they either use or contribute towards building in collaboration with others, increasing the total number of respondents saying that they use such resources as part of their practice.

Do you consult any community-built or externally created resources as part of developing your knowledge around decolonisation?

Figure 12 Do you consult any community-built or externally created resources as part of developing your knowledge around decolonisation?

Survey participants very kindly shared many of the resources they use, which have been compiled in a long list and can be found in the Appendix. It should be noted that this includes content that is publicly available and can be accessed online. Apart from this, there were some references to internal guidelines and other training resources that participants have access to, and which were in line with the type of training mentioned above, but which are not included in the Appendix. Some also mentioned the types of groups they are involved in and which they consider essential part of their professional development in the area, but many are not open to external colleagues; examples of such groups which have a digital presence are included in the resources list (Appendix). As it became evident though the results of the related question (Fig. 13), more than half of participants were active members of decolonisation working or discussion groups (59.02%), while some said that they were not currently, but they plan to join a relevant group (16.39%). A smaller number of respondents answered ‘No’ to this question (11.48%). Most of the respondents choosing ‘Other’ (14.75%), explained that they do not participate in a decolonisation group per se but they regularly join relevant discussions across the library or home institution.

Do you participate in any decolonisation working or discussion groups, either internal or external?

Figure 13 Do you participate in any decolonisation working or discussion groups, either internal or external?

Given the lack of formal decolonisation guidance for libraries, many participants thought that participating in groups where relevant discussions take place is important to understand the landscape and develop individual knowledge, learn what others are doing to avoid duplication of effort, and develop an idea of what constitutes best practice in the area. There are also opportunities to share ideas and collaborate in the context of relevant projects. Participation in internal groups (within the library or home institution) was deemed essential for considering anti-racism in all elements of library practice, from informing collection development policies to making decisions on how collections are presented to users, as well as for aligning library activities with the objectives of the home institution. Another advantage of setting up and engaging with internal groups on the topic is that discussions can move beyond the basics and focus on sharing best practice across the library and home institution and achieve progress. They can also constitute informal support networks for staff involved in this work where a wide group of voices (library professionals, academics, students) can be involved to contribute towards finding solutions to shared problems.

On the other hand, joining external groups (e.g. led by the Student Union) can be useful for gathering feedback and perspectives outside of the library sector. These can have a positive impact on staff confidence as their appreciation of the role of the profession in tackling important issues in education and the broader society increases. RLUK's groups, such as the RLUK Collections Strategy Network and the RLUK Decolonisation Group, were also valued by those participants who were members given their potential for increased impact of their work. Other networks, such as the SCURL EDI network, which have members from different organisations were also recognised for their potential to have sector wide impact. However, some participants noted that these groups, either internal or external, may not necessarily reach all members of staff, such as those in junior roles who are not able to take time out to attend, or those who may not engage in these issues and, thus, may be the ones in most need of support and training.

Thinking about whether survey participants attended events as part of developing their knowledge around decolonisation (Fig. 14), the vast majority said that they do attend relevant events (75.41%), while some said that they planning to attend such events (13.11%). Only few said that they do not attend events as part of developing their knowledge on the topic (6.56%) and even fewer chose 'Other' (4.92%) to explain that they had not attended as much events as they wanted or not at all recently, or that they were attending the meetings of a certain group.

Do you attend relevant events as part of developing your knowledge around decolonisation?

Figure 14 Do you attend relevant events as part of developing your knowledge around decolonisation?

As respondents explained further, attending events, including different types of meetings, workshops, and conferences, can be particularly helpful when thinking about how to get started with decolonisation in the library. Everyone commenting on the value of attending relevant events highlighted their important role in sharing best practice across institutions and the wider sector, learning about what others are doing (from reviewing catalogue descriptions to repatriating collections), gaining inspiration and ideas, as well as enabling institutional benchmarking. A participant noted that, in their institution, colleagues are encouraged to attend events that are related to their role and responsibilities in order to network and learn from others. There was also a comment on the nature of virtual events and the fact that it is often difficult to create the right environment for having difficult conversations.

What are the main challenges around decolonisation training in your library?

Figure 15 Challenges around decolonisation training in RLUK institutions

Regarding the main challenges around decolonisation training, more than half of participants said that they have limited capacity to undertake training (54.10%), while a significant number said that limited or lack of training opportunities constituted a barrier towards further developing their knowledge of the topic (40.98%). Some thought that limited funding to support training was a challenge (14.75%), while others were not sure or did not know (13.11%). Many participants chose ‘Other’ (40.98%) in order to elaborate on their institutional circumstances and the specific challenges they faced.

Thus, based on our findings, it was often a combination of limited time, resources and staff that constituted the main challenge in progressing related activities and discussions, and not just the lack of training opportunities. A participant said that the enthusiasm and interest are often there, but there is insufficient time amongst those at senior management level who make the budget decisions to focus on relevant issues as well as amongst the professionals who lead these activities to keep pushing things forward. In fact, competing priorities combined with the lack of a formal commitment in strategic library objectives can make resourcing or recruiting to support relevant activities very challenging. Another commonly mentioned challenge was that there can, sometimes, be a lack of awareness amongst staff regarding relevant issues and how these relate to them and their roles and, thus, it can be difficult to engage them in decolonisation discussions and make the argument for the necessity of relevant activities. Some referred to the fact that trying to keep up with developments in the area can be overwhelming and that staff may lack the confidence to get started in decolonisation. According to one respondent, there is currently more need for conversations on difficult issues around collection development practices, tools, and services rather than just training on decolonisation, while another argued that, within their institution, other positive and forward-looking activities around EDI map more closely with institutional objectives. Finally, the lack of a diverse workforce, the lack of capacity to build long term links with student communities, and the risk of being seen as political were considered barriers to developing and sustaining decolonisation activity in some research libraries.

Survey participants also reflected on the type of support they currently need to undertake decolonisation activities or achieve progress if already engaged in such initiatives. Given that RLUK institutions are currently at different levels of progress in the process of decolonising collections and practices and, more generally, in making collections more diverse and inclusive, it was often recognised that there is not one solution that can fit all institutional circumstances. Therefore, many participants highlighted the importance of peer support from like-minded colleagues and the need for the development of networks and special interest groups through which staff engaged in related activities can find the support they need. There was also a call for more collaboration and sharing of best practice, such as around supporting the decolonisation of the curriculum, through the sharing of brief case studies from other academic and research libraries. In that way, RLUK member institutions can find ways of creating connections and harness their collective voice and work, as well as identify areas for collaborative work, such as around collaborative cataloguing and editing.

Apart from this, several participants underlined that institutions need to prioritise work on decolonising and formally embed related objectives into strategic plans as this can make resourcing of relevant activities much easier and, thus, will foster progress in the area. Developing the ability to influence and negotiate at the highest level for adequate resourcing will also help to embed practice across the different areas of the home institution. Yet, staff and stakeholder engagement training, for example on how to gently introduce the topic of decolonisation and diversification of resources and have useful conversations on how to approach these, will certainly support the advocacy efforts of the professionals leading relevant activities in the library. Thus, according to some participants, relevant training can also prove beneficial for senior managers and leaders in the library.

Thinking about implementing decolonisation, many would find useful the provision of frameworks and guidance which will cover different areas of practice, such as current methodologies and theory, principles and ethics, engagement and consultation methods (e.g. underrepresented communities), as well as participatory approaches and how to incorporate aspects of decolonisation into information literacy sessions. Providing training and resources addressing these issues can have a positive impact on staff confidence, especially for those who are just starting in decolonisation. More specifically, according to one participant, beginners training around decolonisation for non-academic staff should include information on collection analysis, development, description, and curation; co-creation with students; academic support; understanding staff and staff demographic; understanding the way we teach as well as issues around publishing; and theoretical analysis of the different ways through which western biases and privilege manifest themselves in education and professional practices and services.

Sector wide glossaries, definitions and guidance on terminology can also prove useful given that finding the right language to use when discussing decolonisation was identified as a challenge in many institutions. Others argued that, as part of their practice, they would find helpful the following: online learning objects; visualisation tools; decision trees; tools to assess collections and audit information resources; tools to map collections and identify gaps in terms of content; guidance on measuring and assessing progress and impact of decolonisation activities; as well as guidance on how to decolonise library spaces. Seminars and training workshops with internal facilitators on specific topics, such as managing balance between freedom of expression and censorship, or how to plan for and manage the anti-decolonisation media attention that relevant projects may attract were considered valuable for some.

Regarding modern collection development and the diversification of resources, particularly, several respondents raised the issue of requiring support to obtain materials that are not readily available by usual suppliers. Moreover, some stated that it can be difficult to know what kind of material to buy in certain areas, such as Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), that can support decolonisation efforts. Regarding STEM, specifically, additional support was requested in updating classification systems, contextualising historic collections, and reviewing reading list content. It was argued that, in some disciplines, science is seen as 'objective' and, hence, its knowledge paradigms can not be challenged in the light of the impact of colonisation; professionals supporting academics, researchers, and students in these areas need extra guidance and support on how to persuade certain members of their community that decolonisation work is essential.

Finally, it is worth noting that in order for research libraries to be successful in their decolonisation efforts, relevant changes need to happen at a pedagogical level as well. Thus, the broader Higher Education sector as well as funding organisations will need to take action to support relevant initiatives and advocate for equitable practices and inclusive services, from the way knowledge is produced and published to how it is collected and presented to learners, students, and other audiences.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to explore the current practices and needs of RLUK libraries when making collections more inclusive, with a focus on decolonisation practices and understanding the training needs and skills requirements that staff in member institutions may have. Based on our findings, it became apparent that most RLUK member institutions are engaged in decolonisation activities or activities that aim to make collections more diverse and services and practices more equitable; these can range from collection-focused programmes of activity to actively contributing to the decolonisation of the curriculum in their home institution. Yet, they all seem to be at different levels of progress with a variety of challenges faced in individual institutions depending on the employed approach.

Regarding the role of decolonisation in the library strategic plans, several participating institutions said that they have some type of working definition, statement, or strategy describing the library's intentions with regards to decolonisation or, more generally, to making collections more inclusive and representative of its communities. It should be noted that some libraries were not using the word 'decolonising' to refer to relevant activities in their statements, definitions, and programmes of activity, but used words such as 'diversifying' and 'liberating' collections and practices. On the other hand, many research libraries have not yet embedded decolonisation or relevant initiatives in their strategic objectives, which can cause a number of challenges for the professionals trying to introduce decolonisation practices and activities in the library. These can range from difficulties in justifying the time allocated to build such initiatives and engage in essential training to resourcing and communicating and advocating about the necessity of this work to other library staff and stakeholders.

Thinking about how decolonisation is organised in the library, it became apparent through our results that grassroot decolonisation or equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) groups constitute the main forces in leading discussions and developing relevant initiatives in many RLUK member institutions. Membership of these groups vary across institutions, and it can include staff members from across the different library departments and levels of seniority as well as other professionals, academics, and students from the home institution. Some research libraries frequently consult with members of underrepresented communities as part of their decolonisation efforts. It is worth noting that decolonisation initiatives have been found to be overwhelmingly funded from within the library or home institution. However, a common problem is that relevant activities can be scattered within institutions and, hence, it can be challenging to learn what others are doing and coordinate activity. Therefore, there was often a call for better communication and a more strategic approach to decolonisation within institutions that enables the exchange of ideas and unites decolonisation efforts.

According to the survey results, the professionals leading or supporting decolonisation activities within RLUK institutions came from across the different areas of the library and the majority held medium to high seniority roles. Concerning their confidence levels with regards to decolonisation, most reported medium confidence. Thinking about those who said that they had high confidence, further analysis of their comments showed that there was not a direct link between high confidence and the provision of training alone, as only about half of these participants' institutions provided training. However, direct involvement in decolonisation activities and participation in relevant groups which enabled the sharing of ideas with colleagues, together with events attendance and consultation of training and other relevant resources produced by the broader cultural heritage sector were found to have a positive impact on confidence levels.

On the other hand, in the cases where decolonisation and the development of relevant initiatives were the responsibility of one person or a small group of people, staff confidence was significantly impacted even when colleagues had expertise in the area. The lack of support systems for colleagues involved in relevant activities or difficulties in persuading senior managers about the necessity of decolonisation work had a similar effect to staff confidence and could significantly impede progress.

Generally, and given the lack of formal guidelines and frameworks for libraries on how to implement decolonisation, the majority of professionals in this study were attending events and consulting external resources as a way of further developing their knowledge in the area and learning about what others are doing in the sector. Many participants were also active members of various internal and external groups around decolonisation and EDI; these enabled knowledge exchange and the sharing of best practice and acted as support networks for those involved in relevant activities.

Concerning the type of support they need as part of their practice, many library professionals in this study regarded the support from like-minded colleagues and the sharing of best practice as essential in achieving progress in the area. Prioritising decolonisation work and formally embedding related objectives into strategic plans will make resourcing of relevant activities much easier, while also having a positive impact on staff confidence. Moreover, guidelines and training on how to engage in useful dialogue around decolonisation with library stakeholders would be particularly helpful for many colleagues involved in relevant activities and help communicate the value of this work to other library staff and senior managers in the home institution as well as academics, students, and members of underrepresented communities.

Apart from these, several professionals would find useful guidance around terminology and definitions, as well as frameworks and examples of how to implement decolonisation, from conducting collection analysis, reviewing language in metadata, and assessing the impact of relevant work to buying content to support decolonisation efforts, revising reading list content, and co-curating material with students. There were also arguments that professionals supporting areas such as STEM require additional support given the limited activity in the area and the resistance that colleagues can sometimes encounter by the academic community. However, it should be noted that some of this type of support and training may be better provided by individual institutions, such as supporting staff in engaging with stakeholders and setting up internal groups within the library, while it is more likely for other initiatives, such as developing and sharing glossaries or cases of best practice, to come from the community. Finally, there is space for discussions with others in the broader Higher Education sector as well as the funding sector on how to implement decolonisation at a pedagogical level as well as how to collectively work together to support relevant initiatives and advocate for equitable practices and inclusive services.

CONCLUSION

This report shares the findings of a recent survey led by the RLUK Decolonisation Group which aimed to investigate the current practices and needs of research libraries when making their collections more inclusive and diverse. The focus was placed on decolonisation practices and the needs of staff in terms of training and skills development to support practice in the area. Based on our findings, the majority of RLUK institutions are engaged in decolonisation initiatives or activities that contribute towards diversifying collections and making related practices and services more equitable and inclusive.

However, professionals currently starting in this area or already leading and supporting relevant initiatives in RLUK member libraries reported the need for additional support as part of their practice. Given the lack of formal guidelines for libraries on how to implement decolonisation, library professionals will find different types of support and training helpful, from information on how to get started with reviewing existing collection policies and practices to engaging with stakeholders and contributing to the decolonisation of the curriculum in their home institution. Prioritising decolonisation in library strategic agendas as well as providing spaces where difficult conversations with colleagues and, potentially, stakeholders can take place were considered valuable for achieving progress in the area, coordinating efforts in the home institution, and increasing staff confidence. Sector-wide discussions and conversations with others supporting Higher Education institutions, the sharing of best practice, and identification of collaborative opportunities are also essential for advancing decolonisation work and collectively advocating for inclusive collections and equitable practices.

REFERENCES

- Adebisi, Foluke Ifejola (2019). Why I Say 'Decolonisation is Impossible'. African Skies. Available at: <https://folukeafrica.com/why-i-say-decolonisation-is-impossible/> (accessed 17 July 2023).
- Adebisi, Foluke Ifejola (2020). Decolonising the Law School: Presences, Absences, Silences... and Hope. The Law Teacher, Available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3762558> (accessed 11 July 2023).
- Adefila, Arinola, Vieira Teixeira, Rafael, Morini, Luca, Teixeira Garcia, Maria Lúcia, Zanotti, Tania Mara, Frizzera Delboni, Guerra, Spolander, Gary, and Khalil-Babatunde, Mouzayian (2022). Higher education decolonisation: #Whose voices and their geographical locations? Globalisation, Societies and Education, 20(3), 262-276. DOI: [10.1080/14767724.2021.1887724](https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2021.1887724)
- Bhambra, Gurinder K., Gebrial, Dalia, and Nişancıoğlu, Kerem (Eds.) (2020). Decolonising the University. Pluto Press. Available at: <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/25936> (accessed 11 July 2023).
- Charles, Elizabeth. (2019). Decolonizing the curriculum. Insights: the UKSG journal, 32(1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.475>
- Clarke, Marilyn (2020). Liberate our Library: Doing decolonisation work at Goldsmiths Library. Art Libraries Journal, 45(4), 148-154. DOI:10.1017/alj.2020.23
- Crilly, Jess (2019). Decolonising the library: a theoretical exploration. Spark: UAL Creative Teaching and Learning Journal, 4(1). Available at: <https://sparkjournal.arts.ac.uk/index.php/spark/article/view/123> (accessed 11 July 2023).
- Crilly, Jess and Everitt, Regina (Eds.) (2021). Narrative Expansions. Interpreting Decolonisation in Academic Libraries. Facet Publishing, London, UK.
- Kamposiori, Christina (2022). EDI in the research library. An analysis of RLUK institutions' job descriptions. Research Libraries UK. Available at: <https://www.rluk.ac.uk/rluk-report-edi-in-the-research-library-an-analysis-of-job-descriptions/> (accessed 11 July 2023).
- Kamposiori, Christina (2022). Exploring EDI best practice in libraries and archives. A DCDC22 session report. Research Libraries UK. Available at: <https://www.rluk.ac.uk/exploring-edi-best-practice-in-libraries-and-archives/> (accessed 11 July 2023).
- Wilson, Kevin (2021). Decolonising library collections: contemporary issues, practical steps and examples from London School of Economics. In: Crilly, Jess and Everitt, Regina, (Eds.) Narrative Expansions: Interpreting Decolonisation in Academic Libraries. Facet Publishing, London, UK, pp. 225-250.
- Winter, Jennie, Webb, Oliver, and Turner, Rebecca (2022). Decolonising the curriculum: A survey of current practice in a modern UK university. Innovations in Education and Teaching International. DOI: [10.1080/14703297.2022.2121305](https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2022.2121305)

APPENDIX

This resource pack was created based on the information submitted by professionals participating in the RLUK Developing Inclusive Collections survey.

These resources will be useful for colleagues currently undertaking or looking to start decolonisation activities within their institutions, or those with a professional interest in decolonisation across libraries and the academic and research sectors.

Seminars/ Events/ Courses:

- Centre for Data, Culture & Society CDCS, University of Edinburgh, <https://www.cdcs.ed.ac.uk/>
- Future Learn Course on ‘Decolonising Education: From Theory to Practice’ by the University of Bristol, <https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/decolonising-education-from-theory-to-practice>
- ‘Inclusive Collections, Inclusive Libraries’ Seminar Series, Research Libraries UK, <https://www.rluk.ac.uk/icil/>
- University of Cambridge Museums, <https://www.museums.cam.ac.uk/theme/power-and-memory>
- Mapping the Road Towards Archival Justice: inclusive terminology and colonial archives, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Jqrv0a0SbfI>
- EACF’s Decolonising Conservation and Collections Management Symposium, <https://www.icon.org.uk/events/eacf-conservation-network-collections-management-network-symposium.html>
- ARLIS-UK Ethical Cataloguing Lunchtime Webinar series, <https://arlis.net/arlis-cataloguing-and-classification-committee-ethics-series-2/>
- Archives for Learning and Education Section’s (ALES) training events, <https://www.archives.org.uk/training-events/vvs1177iqzldn7bp3wp6rvkrydm8lp#:~:text=The%20next%20ALES%20training%20event,and%20a%20queer%20history%20activist.>
- IFLA ARL Webinar series: Decolonization in education: role of the academic library, <https://www.ifla.org/events/ifla-arl-webinar-series-decolonization-in-education-role-of-the-academic-library/>
- Cambridge Digital Humanities events, <https://www.cdh.cam.ac.uk/events/>
- SCONUL/ Advance HE - Leading change on race equality, <https://www.sconul.ac.uk/page/advance-he-leading-change-on-race-equality>
- Talis Aspire User Group Events - <https://talis.com/talis-aspire-user-group/>

Guides, statements, strategies and other resources:

- Imperial College London: Geographic bias in curricula, <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/admin-services/library/learning-support/geo-bias/>
- Netherland’s National Museum for World Cultures, Words Matter: https://issuu.com/tropenmuseum/docs/wordsmatter_english
- Archives for Black Lives in Philadelphia, Anti-Racist Description Resources: https://archivesforblacklives.files.wordpress.com/2019/10/ardr_final.pdf
- Guide to Using Special Collections at Yale University, Statement on Harmful Language in Archival Description: <https://guides.library.yale.edu/specialcollections/statementondescription>
- ARA, Emotional Support Guidelines: <https://www.archives.org.uk/health-wellbeing>

- University of Leeds, Sensitive Language in Archive Description: <https://leedsunilibrary.wordpress.com/2021/05/26/sensitive-language-in-archive-description/>
- University of Liverpool, Decolonising the Curriculum Toolkit, <https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/centre-for-innovation-in-education/resources/all-resources/decolonising-the-curriculum.html>
- John Rylands Library (Manchester University), Rylands Reflects: Diversifying Collections and Practices: <https://rylandscollections.com/2020/08/21/rylands-reflects-diversifying-collections-and-practices/>
- University of Manchester Library statement: <https://www.manchester.ac.uk/discover/news/diversifying-collections-and-practices-at-the-university-of-manchester-library/>
- University of Manchester Library RACE Centre: <https://www.library.manchester.ac.uk/aiu-race-centre/>
- Cambridge University Library statement: <https://www.lib.cam.ac.uk/about-library/diversifying-collections-and-practices>
- Lancaster University Library, Diversifying the Library: <https://lancaster.libguides.com/c.php?g=668370&p=4741616>
- Newcastle University Library, Diversifying the curriculum, <https://libguides.ncl.ac.uk/edi/diversify>
- LIS-DECOLONISE JiscMail List, <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?A0=LIS-DECOLONISE>
- ARCHIVES-NRA Archives JiscMail List, <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/wa.exe?A2=ARCHIVES-NRA;64fddb7c.1006>
- OCLC, Reimagine Descriptive Workflows Cataloguing Code of Ethics, <https://www.oclc.org/content/dam/research/publications/2022/oclcresearch-reimagine-descriptive-workflows-a4.pdf>
- University of Kent, Diversity Mark toolkit: <https://blogs.kent.ac.uk/diversitymarktoolkit/2020/10/16/welcome-to-the-diversity-mark-toolkit/>
- Museums Association, <https://www.museumsassociation.org/campaigns/decolonising-museums/>
- Cilip Information Professional: <https://www.cilip.org.uk/news/605611/Decolonising-the-library-Making-space-for-new-narratives.htm>
- ARL Diversity, Equity and Inclusion: <https://www.arl.org/category/our-priorities/diversity-equity-inclusion/>
- ACRL Equity, Diversity and Inclusion: <https://www.ala.org/acrl/issues/edi>
- ARLIS Equity Steering Group: <https://arlis.net/committees-groups/equity-steering-group/>
- Museum Detox : <https://www.museumdetox.org/about-us>
- University of the West of England, Narrative Expansions: Interpreting Decolonisation in Academic Libraries, <https://www.uwe.ac.uk/study/library/our-libraries/library-activities-and-groups/decolonising-your-library>
- Goldsmiths University Library, Liberate our Library: <https://www.gold.ac.uk/library/about/liberate-our-library/>
- Sussex University Library, Decolonisation Statement' : <https://www.sussex.ac.uk/library/about/strategy/decolonisation>
- University of Sheffield, Library Comprehensive Content Strategy, <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/library/about/content-strategy>
- Decolonising SOAS Library, <https://soas.libguides.com/c.php?g=705259&p=5079430>
- SOAS, Decolonising SOAS Learning and Teaching Toolkit for Programme and Module Convenors, <https://blogs.soas.ac.uk/decolonisingsoas/files/2018/10/Decolonising-SOAS-Learning-and-Teaching-Toolkit-AB.pdf>

- University of Oxford, Anti-Racism in Academia: Decolonizing the Curriculum, <https://libguides.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/c.php?g=686589&p=4907734>
- Harvard Medical School, 'Guidelines for Inclusive and Conscientious Description', <https://wiki.harvard.edu/confluence/display/hmschommanual/Guidelines+for+Inclusive+and+Conscientious+Description>
- Yale University Library, Reparative archival description, <https://guides.library.yale.edu/reparativearchivaldescription>
- University of Arts London: Decolonising reading lists guide, https://www.arts.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0021/201936/Decolonising-reading-lists-PDF-703KB.pdf
- University of Exeter: Decolonising your reading list, <https://libguides.exeter.ac.uk/c.php?g=688140&p=4922669>
- Manchester Metropolitan University, Decolonising the Curriculum Toolkit, <https://www.mmu.ac.uk/about-us/professional-services/uta/reducing-awarding-gaps/decolonising-the-curriculum-toolkit>
- Manchester Metropolitan University, Reading List Diversity Audit, <https://www.mmu.ac.uk/library/using-the-library/celebrating-diversity/reading-list-diversity-audit>
- University of Leeds, <https://studenteddev.leeds.ac.uk/developing-practice/decolonising/decolonising-reading-list/>
- LSE Library, <https://www.lse.ac.uk/africa/decolonisation-hub/Decolonisation-resources>
- Cambridge University Library, <https://decolonisingthroughcriticallibrarianship.wordpress.com/>
- Dartmouth Library, <https://www.library.dartmouth.edu/digital/digital-collections/change-the-subject>
- The National Archives, Language and the catalogue: Offensive terminology in archival descriptions, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XWoPUHQMqDQ>
- Decolonising Bristol Medical School, <http://decolbms.org.uk/>
- University of Aberdeen, Resources, <https://www.abdn.ac.uk/staffnet/working-here/resources-12592.php>
- University of Aberdeen, Antiracism Strategy 2022-2025, <https://www.abdn.ac.uk/staffnet/documents/Antiracism%20Strategy.pdf>
- University of Aberdeen, Decolonising the Curriculum Steering Group, <https://www.abdn.ac.uk/staffnet/governance/decolonising-and-enhancing-the-curriculum-steering-group-13989.php>
- University of Reading, Decolonising the Curriculum resources, <https://www.reading.ac.uk/diversity/-/media/project/functions/diversity/documents/resources-to-decolonise-curriculum.pdf>
- University of York, Decolonising and diversifying Reading Lists toolkit, <https://subjectguides.york.ac.uk/readinglists/diversity>
- Mercian Collaboration, Reflecting on Decolonising the Academic Library, <https://merciancollaboration.org.uk/reflecting-decolonising-academic-library>
- University of East Anglia Library, Decolonisation: About this Guide <https://uea-uk.libguides.com/decolonisation>
- University of Leicester, Inclusive Collections, <https://le.ac.uk/library/about/policies/inclusive-collections>
- University of Warwick, Anti-Racist Pedagogy and Process in HE, https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/cross_fac/academy/activities/learningcircles/anti-racistpedagogyandprocess/
- University of Durham, Durham University Race Equality Charter Action Plan (2022-2025), <https://www.durham.ac.uk/media/durham-university/professional-services/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/DU-REC-Action-Plan-MASTER-Nov2022.pdf>

Papers/ Reports/ Blogs:

- Sofia Akel (2020). 'What Decolonising The Curriculum Really Means', Each Other, <https://eachother.org.uk/decolonising-the-curriculum-what-it-really-means/>
- New Scots Refugee Integration Strategy, <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2018/01/new-scots-refugee-integration-strategy-2018-2022-summary/documents/00530086-pdf/00530086-pdf/govscot%3Adocument/00530086.pdf>
- Clarke, M. (2020). Liberate our Library: Doing decolonisation work at Goldsmiths Library. *Art Libraries Journal*, 45(4), 148-154. doi:[10.1017/alj.2020.23](https://doi.org/10.1017/alj.2020.23)
- Research Libraries UK, Exploring EDI best practice in libraries and archives. A DCDC22 session report, <https://www.rluk.ac.uk/exploring-edi-best-practice-in-libraries-and-archives/>
- Chilcott, Alicia (2019). 'Towards protocols for describing racially offensive language in UK public archives', *Archival Science*, vol. 19, pp. 359–376. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs10502-019-09314-y>
- On History, 'What's in a name?': cataloguing in a decolonising library: <https://blog.history.ac.uk/2020/05/whats-in-a-name-cataloguing-in-a-decolonising-library/>
- 'Archives and Records' special issue 42.3 (2021)
- Campbell, Paul Ian, Ajour, Ashjan, Dunn, Andre' Karavadra, Heena' Nockels, Keith, and Whittaker, Sarah (2022). Evaluating the Racially Inclusive Curricula Toolkit in HE': Empirically Measuring the Efficacy and Impact of Making Curriculum-content Racially Inclusive on the Educative Experiences of Students of Colour in the UK. University of Leicester. Report. <https://doi.org/10.25392/leicester.data.21724658.v1>
- Dalal-Clayton, Anjalie and Puri Purini, Ilaria (2022). Doing the Work: Embedding Anti-Racism and Decolonisation in Museum Practice. Contemporary Art Society and UAL Decolonising Arts Institute, London, UK. <https://ualresearchonline.arts.ac.uk/id/eprint/18511/>
- LSE Library, <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2019/10/04/how-to-decolonise-the-library/>
- Carissa Chew, 'Histories of colour, <https://historiesofcolour.co.uk/>
- ARA, Diversity and Inclusion, <https://www.archives.org.uk/news/tag/Decolonising+Blogs>

Projects:

- Museums Galleries Scotland, Empire, Slavery & Scotland's Museums, <https://www.museumsgalleriesscotland.org.uk/project/empire-slavery-scotlands-museums/>
- The University of Edinburgh, 'Uncovered', <https://www.ed.ac.uk/global/uncovered>
- University of Leeds, Gypsy, Traveller and Roma Collections, <https://library.leeds.ac.uk/special-collections/collection/702>

Conferences:

- DCDC Conference, <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/dcdc-conference>
- UKSG Conference, <https://www.uksg.org/events/annualconference>
- WHELP Conference, <https://whelf.ac.uk/excluded-voices-2022/>
- RLUK Conference, <https://rlukconference.com/>
- Critical Approaches to Libraries Conference, <https://sites.google.com/view/calconference>
- SCURL EDI Conference, <https://www.youtube.com/@scurl4221>
- Museums Association Conference, <https://www.museumsassociation.org/events/conference-2023/>
- Art Libraries Society UK conference, <https://arlis.net/news-events/conferences-2/>

Best practice examples:

- Recollecting Empire Exhibition, St-Andrews University, <https://re-collecting-empire.wp.st-andrews.ac.uk/>
- Temi Odumosu (2022). 'The Crying Child, On Colonial Archives, Digitization, and Ethics of Care in the Cultural Commons', *Current Anthropology: Atlantic Slavery and the Making of the Modern World*, 61(S22), <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/toc/ca/2020/61/S22>
- Cambridge University Library, Decolonisation-related library and archive work in Cambridge: a framework, <https://www.lib.cam.ac.uk/about-library/diversifying-collections-and-practices/cambridge-university-libraries-decolonisation-0>
- Decolonisation Best Practice and Case Studies in HE Libraries, Google Sheets, <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1NyBVaHlJKTrLM9S1tCfSv8rIDwpqpx5A0mkgAKiSY2g/edit#gid=0>
- Carissa Chew's/National Library of Scotland, 'Inclusive Terminology Glossary', https://docs.google.com/document/d/17W4hstjFFlWRdD5gWjx0WdKuqzUHMqat9zyIAjgW_X8/edit
- Decolonisation begins on your own bookshelf, <https://www.gold.ac.uk/study/creating-change/visibility/deirdre-osborne/#:~:text=The%20importance%20of%20decolonisation,racial%20justice%20into%20our%20programmes>
- Cambridge Medical Library, Themed Reading Lists, <https://library.medschl.cam.ac.uk/search-and-find/themed-reading-lists/>
- Leeds University Libraries, Introducing the LGBTQ+ Archives Project. How can we move towards a more inclusive community history?, <https://leedsunilibrary.wordpress.com/2022/02/23/introducing-the-lgbtq-archives-project-how-can-we-move-towards-a-more-inclusive-community-history/>

